

The Use of Blockchain Technology in Smart Logistics

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Abstract—Many fields have expedited the digitization process in the age of Industry 4.0. Digital Supply Chain, Logistics 4.0, and Marketing 4.0 are just a few examples of this. For the first time in 2008, the foundations of a new digital transfer system were built with the first virtual crypto money transfer without the use of a middleman. Despite the fact that the basics of Blockchain technology are projected to alter in the financial sector, it is expected to be applied in a variety of areas in the near future. The purpose of this study is to examine the innovations brought about by Blockchain technology in smart logistics operations and to measure awareness. The significance of this study is that Blockchain technology's characteristics are not well-designed in the field of smart logistics. The paper explains the features of smart logistics and Blockchain technology, as well as how Blockchain technology's advancements may help with smart logistics applications. Transparency, security, and traceability are just a few of the advantages of blockchain technology.

Index Terms—Smart Logistics, Blockchain, Smart Contracts

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology's driving power has resulted in new industrial advancements in the sphere of manufacturing. The fourth industrial revolution, sometimes known as Industry 4.0, began in 2011. The most compelling rationale for moving to Industry 4.0 is because machines can be manufactured without requiring human cooperation. The enterprise's production, supply, logistics, marketing, and resources are all linked together like chain links. All business operations are linked together like chain links that follow each other like the chain connected to the machine's gears. The Blockchain works in the same way that a machine's modification of a chain link provides a driving and attracting force for the change of other links.

This development has had an impact on logistics activities, which serve as a vital connection between the producer and the consumer in the supply chain. The ability of real-time operations and information flow in manufacturing processes to run simultaneously has a considerable impact on logistics performance. It can offer information about the reality of the house's wall color in harmony with the design as a consequence of an order received from a client generating sales by producing virtual reality according to the customer's needs. In smart logistics operations, Blockchain technology allows customers to communicate a variety of information with one another, such as the product's production phases and when it will arrive at the customer's house.

The logistics operations are the most significant differentiators in the competitive climate of businesses. The manufacture of a product at the appropriate time and in the correct place is referred to as logistics (Tanga & Veelenturf, 2019: 4). Many people consider the time spent waiting for a consumer to purchase a product to be an unnecessary and unpleasant activity. Alibaba, which operates the world's largest e-commerce network, spent \$15 billion in 2017 on logistics chain network management to better manage these procedures (www.forbes.com, 2020). According to the Buchman 2018 research, Amazon has 486 distribution locations throughout the world, hundreds of vehicles, and 32 Boeing 767 planes to better manage logistical waiting times (Buchman, 2018). The biggest distinguishing aspect of the Amazon and Alibaba brands is that their logistics infrastructures are in better shape than their competitors' and that they effectively manage their logistics procedures.

Crypto money transfer was explicitly detailed in a 2013 paper authored by Satoshi Nakamoto, who built the foundations of blockchain technology. For the first time in 2014, assets (cryptocurrency) were exchanged between two persons. Many academics afterwards proposed that Blockchain technology might not be restricted to asset transfers or digital money transfers. In this context, Blockchain technology is being used to transmit data, documents, images, and a variety of other digital items.

Big data and cloud computing technologies are now playing a major role in Industry 4.0 and Logistics 4.0 operations. It is predicted that as blockchain technology advances, it will eventually supplant big data and cloud computing technologies. It is critical in logistics management that the activity served and the flow of information be continuous. By making it difficult, blockchain is a secure information recording technology that makes it hard to manipulate, hack, or defraud a utilized system. A Blockchain is simply a digital ledger in which transactions are recorded and duplicated across the Blockchain's network of all computer systems. This notebook secures data and information for the user.

The blockchain technology's transparent structure and cryptography, as well as the decentralized nature of the information flow between the participants, provide significant prospects for trust and real-time communication. Furthermore, Blockchain aids in the speeding up of international commercial financial money transfer activities. By removing middleman organizations, international logistics companies may undertake service operations and payments swiftly and securely with mutual agreements. Many organizations and enterprises are making virtual crypto money transfers at the moment. Given that the media has speculated that the central bank would issue digital currency in the near future, procedures in logistics can be controlled intelligently by employing Blockchain technology.

The implications of Blockchain technology on smart logistics operations were evaluated in this study. A literature review was conducted in the first part of the six-part research, and the conceptual framework of smart logistics, Blockchain, and smart contracts were discussed in the second, third, and fourth sections, respectively. The fifth section discusses smart logistics and Blockchain technology applications. The results

and overall evaluations are presented in the study's sixth and final section.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Due to the fact that blockchain technology is a relatively new application, investigations were done between 2016 and 2020. Table 1 summarizes studies on Blockchain technology that include logistics and supply chain.

Table 1. Studies Covering Blockchain Technology in the Field of Supply Chain and Logistics

Writers	Subject	Scope	Content
Tian, (2016)	Agri-food supply chain traceability system for China based on RFID and Blockchain Technology	Blockchain technology focuses on traceability in the creation of the agricultural supply chain.	From the beginning of the products grown in the agricultural field, a barcode of each product is created with RFID technology. The ease of tracking these products from the beginning to the retailer is explained.
Gromovs vs Lammi (2017)	The necessity of Blockchain internet in innovative logistics education	The reason why the Internet of Things and Blockchain Technologies are included in the scope of innovative logistics.	Within the scope of innovative logistics approaches, it provides information about technologies such as Blockchain, Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence and what kind of topics will be trending in logistics in the future.
Álvarez-Díaz vd., (2017)	Smart contracts and Blockchain for logistics management	It has been evaluated how smart contract and Blockchain Technology can be used	Based on the features of the smart contract ethereum crypto money, which was first released in 2017, she made some

		in logistics management and what benefits it will provide.	constructs on the benefits of the Blockchain bases, which will be used for logistics management.
Liao Wang, (2018)	Blockchain in the entertainment industry Applied logistics management	The evaluation of the blockchain-based logistics management system has been adapted to the entertainment industry.	The applications of ICE company in the logistics 4.0 process in the field of tourism and entertainment in a traceable, fast and safe way are presented. He evaluated the benefits of the concentric valuation business model with the establishment of a Blockchain-based system in the Logistics 4.0 process.
Peterse n VD., (2018)	Mapping opportunities : Blockchain in supply chain and logistics	It includes the opportunities offered by Blockchain in the field of supply chain and logistics.	It shows the integration of the latest developments in the field of supply chain and logistics with Blockchain technology. Thanks to the blockchain technology, he evaluated the traceability of the activities, the centrality of the products and the ease of the financial processes.
Perboli vd., (2018)	Blockchain in logistics and supply chain: real-world implementati	It has integrated Blockchain Technology with innovations	He evaluated the use of blockchain technology in logistics and supply chain in

	on with a lean approach	in logistics and supply chain.	the financial field, secondly in fresh vegetable distribution, and finally in terms of cost reduction.
Yi, (2019)	A security model in logistics: Blockchain	It includes evaluations of Blockchain Based logistics management on trust.	Concentrating on the transparency and cryptology feature of the Blockchain, the benefits are explained in order to make innovative logistics activities more secure and to reduce the risk level.
Pal & Kant, (2019)	Internet of Things in Food Logistics, Source Traceability Using Blockchain	In food logistics, an evaluation is made on traceability and traceability with the Internet of Things by using Blockchain.	Supply and demand assessment in the fresh vegetable and food industry has evaluated the establishment of a Blockchain-based system on the traceability of food.
Gurtu & Johnny, (2019)	Blockchain Potential in supply chain management: literature review	Content analysis was carried out on the researched studies related to Blockchain in supply chain and logistics activities.	Industry 4.0 building blocks used in supply chain and logistics activities and studies that construct the use of Blockchain have been examined. After completing the important shortcomings of blockchain technology in the future, it has been used in many network systems (logistics, health,

			education, etc.).
Betti vd., (2019)	Development of hyper-connected logistics with blockchain and smart contracts	An evaluation has been made on the establishment of a hyper-connected logistics network through blockchain and smart contracts.	It is planned to establish a hyper-connected logistics network by establishing inter-object communication with the coordination of blockchain-based , smart contract and internet of things technologies.
Helo & Shamsuzzoha, (2020).	Distribution architecture with real-time supply chain-Blockchain	Logistics networks to be built on real-time and equivalent traceability have been examined.	The Internet of Things, Blockchain, RFID technologies used in Logistics 4.0 have integrated the simultaneous distribution tracking and secure traceability setup into the transportation routes.
Kodym vd., (2020).	Associating Logistics 4.0 risks and minimizing these risks with Blockchain	The potential risks of Logistics 4.0 have been evaluated. Ways to reduce these risks with Blockchain Technology have been examined.	Cyber attacks constitute the weakest structures of cyber-connected systems in the Internet of Things. In terms of security, the cryptology and immutable nature of the blockchain reduce the risks.
Astarita vd., (2020).	Literature review of blockchain-based systems in transportation	Academic studies on Blockchain in the field of transportation have	Studies on Blockchain technologies under the main headings of supply chain, logistics and

		been examined.	transportation have been examined. The most used terms were examined with content analysis and the density of article researches related to Blockchain was examined to shed light on future studies.
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Figure 2. Intelligent Logistics Basic Structure (McFarlane et al., 2016:107)

The goal of smart logistics is to make optimal use of planning and programming. Smart logistics planning and scheduling procedures are supported by ICT infrastructure, manufacturer regulations, and government policies that provide essential information resources at the proper time and place (Jabeur et al., 2017:673). initiates the procedure. It has numerous favorable impacts in this procedure, such as decreasing mistakes and being immediate in the process. Each application has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. Table 2 assesses the advantages and disadvantages of smart logistics (Karagöz & Doyduk, 2020:46).

III. SMART LOGISTICS

Logistics refers to the actions involved in moving products or commodities from a central location to a destination utilizing a variety of resources such as people, vehicles, buildings, and equipment (Li & Ma, 2020: 6193). Logistics serves as a vital link between production and consumption. In transportation processes, the logistics industry employs main and secondary energy sources such as coal, gasoline, diesel, fuel oil, natural gas, heat, and electricity (Pan et al., 2020: 2).

The internet of things, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, big data, small data, cyber systems technology production system, which is the driving force of the Industry 4.0 process, have all evolved intelligent systems and technologies. The employment of these technologies has become vital as the management of processes associated to logistical operations, such as the supply of raw materials required for manufacturing and the meeting of the generated items with the customer, has grown increasingly complicated. Technological improvements in logistics and logistics management have been dubbed "Smart Logistics" or "Logistics 4.0" as a result of the fourth industrial revolution (Issaoui, et al., 2019:267). Figure 1 depicts the many stages of logistics evolution.

Table 2. Opportunities, Threats, Strengths and Weaknesses of Logistics 4.0 Applications

Figure 1. Stages of Logistics Evolution (Galindo, 2016: 25)

Intelligent logistics is utilized in conjunction with powerful artificial intelligence solutions based on new smart technologies, as well as computer support systems that allow for complete process automation (Kauf, 2019:146). Figure 2 depicts the main techniques necessary in the execution of smart logistics that provide smart solutions.

Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability / Tracking full automation Speed Simultaneous data sharing Cost advantage Increase in the amount of goods and services Increase in control power effective communication systems Integration with foreign markets blockchain applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insufficient infrastructure to meet the needs Length of the process Cost investment requirement traditional approaches Technology integration issues Hackers and security threats Making room for foreign competitors by staying out of technology incorrect use
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction of costs customer loyalty employee productivity Service diversity service quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The general belief that it will have a negative impact on employment Inadequacy of financial, sectoral

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Changing the ways of doing business ● More efficient operation ● value added chain ● Preventing human-induced errors in particular 	<p>and public platforms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inadequacy of the incentive system ● investment cost ● Non-standard internet connections
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built in blocks are encrypted. The Blockchain participants are the only ones who can see the cryptocurrency structures. It is quite rare that a crypto structure would be dissolved and that other parties will interfere with transactions if this is done in this manner. The addition of a new participant to the block structure results in the construction of additional blocks. In terms of security, each additional participant necessitates the breach of cryptology security. The security power of a group grows as the number of participants grows.

IV. BLOCKCHAIN

The goal of smart logistics is to make optimal use of planning and programming. Smart logistics planning and scheduling procedures are supported by ICT infrastructure, manufacturer regulations, and government policies that provide essential information resources at the proper time and place (Jabeur et al., 2017:673). initiates the procedure. It has numerous favorable impacts in this procedure, such as decreasing mistakes and being immediate in the process. Each application has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. Table 2 assesses the advantages and disadvantages of smart logistics (Karagöz & Doyduk, 2020:46).It goes to the next block, the identical transactions are repeated in each block, and the transfer is completed as a consequence of the approval of the nodes (each participant) that construct money transfer blocks in blockchain technology. To transfer assets, the recipient transmits a lock (crypto structure) to the sender. The sender gets the desired amount from the receiver in encrypted form. Other nodes in the system verify these people's digital signatures and authorize the transfer. All blocks continue this process (Usta & Dogantekin, 2017:39).

Bitcoin crypto money technology, which is the first blockchain creation, allows money to be transferred without the involvement of banks or other parties. The data is recorded in a dispersed account structure that is visible to all participants. Crypto algorithms are less dangerous in terms of security than the present financial structure due to Bitcoin's transparency. Apart from asset transfers, blockchain technology has a wide range of applications. It may be used for a variety of data transfers, such as pdf, e-mail, and photographs, for example. The fact that all parties can view the encrypted data thanks to blockchain technology strengthens the sense of confidence in the system.

4.1. FEATURES OF BLOCKCHAIN

The advent of crypto currency has piqued the interest of firms developing Blockchain technology, as well as the financial industry. The Blockchain's properties are the primary cause for this emphasis. These include cryptographic structure, transparency, and one-to-one transactions. These properties, it may be argued, open the door for Blockchain technology to be applied in fields other than digital money transmission.

4.1.1. CRYPTOLOGY

The identities of the people who make up the blocks are formed using a specific algorithm. All of the structures that are

4.1.2. TRANSPARENCY

Transparency in the blockchain structure is created by the fact that every transfer transaction done in the blockchain is visible to all participants. The notion of transparency ensures that the transactions carried out within the blocks are under supervision. After the participants in the blocks have approved the transfer operations, the transactions take occur. Data and asset transfer occurs as a consequence of the permission of a specified number of participants.

4.1.3. PERSON-TO-PERSON TRANSFER

Without the use of third parties, transactions may be carried directly between the sender and the recipient on the blockchain. In this procedure, there is no supervisory, corrective, or centralized structure. The participants in the Blockchain must authorize the transactions in order for them to be carried through. There are just two choices: complete the transaction or not. Although the absence of corrective action is a beneficial attribute for transaction security, it is a bad feature.

V. SMART CONTRACTS

"Agreed, self-executing agreements that can be represented by programmable codes of transacting users" is how smart contracts are characterized (Wangvd., 2019:23). The execution of codes by the transacting parties aids the transfer. Because smart contracts are an element of the Blockchain, they may be said to make asset transfers easier and faster. Smart contracts have been established on Ethereum, Hyperledger, and other Blockchain systems (Clack et al., 2016:2). The transaction speed has increased and the transaction time has decreased thanks to smart contracts.

Many academics are working on smart contracts in order to improve confidence in Blockchain's decentralized structure and lower transaction costs (Vinayak et al., 2019:1024). Industry 4.0 will continue to leverage Blockchain and smart contracts in field-specific integrated research. One of the most fundamental functions of smart contracts is to boost the speed of data transmission according to the intended usage by reducing the time spent on specific security steps during virtual asset transfer.

VI. SMART LOGISTICS AND BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY APPLICATIONS

Aside from the virtual money transfer model created in the digital era, there have been several studies on how blockchain technology may be implemented in other sectors. It was

examined in this study how to change logistics networks and management.

Blockchain technology may emphasize and elaborate at least five essential product dimensions: nature (what it is), quality (how it is), quantity (how much), location (where it is) and ownership (who possesses it at all times) (Saber et al., 2019, p. 2120). It builds trust in the decentralized structure that controls the system and processes in this way. Inspection of the uninterrupted monitoring chain may be ensured by the contact between the raw material suppliers and the end user in the logistics and supply chain network.

Smart contracts are computer programmes that specify the rules for creating blocks in the Blockchain. Smart contracts are the establishment of the essential rules and regulations in the network architecture, which are transparent to all parties (Tian, 2017: 4). Blockchain technology, unlike large data and cloud computing, increases awareness due to its decentralized and transparent nature. The real-time sharing and recording of actions where things are bought, sold, and delivered is the smart contract between two trade partners.

Supply Chain

Figure 3. Transformation of the Supply Chain (Saber et al., 2019: 2121).

The information and product movement in a typical logistics and supply chain is linear. In blockchain-based systems, it is cyclical. The fact that the blockchain basis is visible is the most fundamental factor for this structure's cyclical nature. Transparency guarantees that all modes of transportation work together. With each member in the system, the security of this crypto-based structure grows exponentially. Every new user of blockchain technology is referred to as a node. A freshly formed crypto structure is represented by this node.

While some routes in the logistics and supply chain exchange information indirectly, others exchange information directly. The link between logistical activities will be realized immediately thanks to blockchain technology. As a result, it

will help the speedy completion of logistical activities and the saving of time.

With the internet of things, RFID (Radio-Frequency Identification) systems may be used to identify objects, allowing transactions to be carried out properly and rapidly without the need for staff (humans). The RFID technology is used extensively in the agriculture and food logistics industries. The radio frequency number assigned to a product during manufacture aids in tracking it until it reaches the consumer. The data (specified radio frequency) cannot be updated or modified using blockchain technology. The traceability and dependability of agricultural items may be efficiently carried out using RFID and Blockchain technologies (Tian, 2016: 3). Real-time tracking of agricultural products from seed to customer is possible because of RFID.

Figure 4. Potential Blockchain Technologies in Logistics (Tijan, et al., 2019:9)

Production-centered logistics operations must be followed in order to assure traceability of agricultural products, pharmaceuticals, and luxury goods. Because of the openness and immutability of blockchain technology, all steps of these items' manufacture can be tracked from start to finish. The internet of things technology is meant to successfully monitor the process from product creation to distribution to the customer without requiring human intervention.

Figure 5. Blockchain Concentric Value Environment for ICE Firm (Liao Wang, 2018:10)

For the ICE firm, which has significant tourism-related operations, a Blockchain and concentric value framework has been developed. The introduction of real-time traceability of all logistical activities is the most significant contribution of blockchain technology (Liao & Wang, 2018:10). The blockchain-based business model is demonstrated in conjunction with the technology employed in the logistics 4.0 process. Many technological transactions, like the internet of things, artificial intelligence, smart transportation, and autonomous robotics, contribute significantly to the right location at the right time.

VII. CONCLUSION

The supply and logistics departments, which connect marketing and manufacturing in the Industry 4.0 process, must swiftly adapt to technological advancements. This adaptation can only take place in tandem with technological advancements. Big data, the internet of things, artificial intelligence, 5G technology, tiny data, and Blockchain technology are all part of the Logistics 4.0 process.

The benefits of blockchain technology include smart contracts, transparency, cryptography, and a decentralized structure. These capabilities are solely meant to be used in the financial area for digital virtual money transfers. The application of blockchain technology in smart logistics operations such as information flow, product tracking, and funding transfer is expected to result in significant changes and increased awareness.

It is hoped that smart contracts would speed up transaction times. The processes of the transacting parties are visible to the participants who produce the blocks. The control and security systems arise naturally due to the blocks' transparent nature. The middleman institutions of smart logistics transactions are eliminated thanks to the smart contracts and transparency features of blockchain technology. Transactions are also completed in less time due to the elimination of middleman institutions.

The real-time operation flow is visible to all participants in the logistics network established by the blocks, allowing them to estimate time. This approach allows retailers, particularly in the agriculture industry, to observe the entire process from seed to customer. The transparency aspect is seen to be a good safeguard against dubious items or deceit.

Communication between objects is established and information flow is ensured by means of communication between objects for operations such as handling, packaging, and distribution, which are smart logistics activities, without the need for manpower, using the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) feature. Because all transactions are recorded and not discarded, the logistical operations are preserved for as long as the blocks remain in use. The internet of things, machine learning, and blockchain technology are likely to revolutionize the logistics industry in the future.

Compliance with the Ethical Standard

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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